
Customer Relationship Management and the Performance of Deposit Money Banks in South-East, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of customer relationship management the performance of deposit money banks in South-East, Nigeria. The study specifically aimed to examine the effect of customer attraction on marketing; investigate the influence of services quality management on financial performance; assess the effect of technological innovation on task performance; determine the influence of customer retention on operational performance, establish the effect of customer satisfaction on contextual performance and ascertain the effect of customer orientation on product performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. Relevant conceptual theoretical and empirical literatures were reviewed. The study was anchored on Contingency Theory and Institutional Theory. Survey research design was adopted. This study was carried out in South East Nigeria. South-East consists of Abia State, Anambra State, Ebonyi State, Enugu State and Imo State. This study makes use of primary source data. The population of the study comprises 2633 the employees and management staff of deposit money banks in South-East. The statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall was employed to determine the sample size of 529. The instrument used for the study was questionnaire. Face and content validity were adopted while, test re-test and Cronbach Alpha method was carried out to achieve reliability of the instrument. Simple percentage analysis was employed to analyze the research questions and the study employed Linear multiple regression analysis to test hypotheses. The results showed that customer attraction has a significant positive effect on effect marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. ($t = 16.431$; $p = 0.000$); services quality management has a significant positive effect on financial performance of deposit banks ($t = 22.613$; $p = 0.000$); technological innovation has a significant positive effect on task performance of deposit banks ($t = 17.959$; $p = 0.000$); customer retention has significant positive effect on operational performance of deposit banks ($t = 29.023$; $p = 0.000$); customer satisfaction has no significant positive effect on contextual performance of deposit banks ($t = 23.398$; $p = 0.000$) and customer orientation has a significant positive effect product performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria ($t = 11.454$ and $p = 0.000$). The study concluded that that customer relationship management has significant effect performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. The study recommended that bank management should embark on building a stronger customer attraction since it has been established that it contributes significantly to performance of deposit banks. Bank management should develop strategies to improve service quality such as meeting customers desired service levels, improving the quality services, to meet customers' needs. Organizations must not only acquire the most recent and useful technology but must also train and retrain their employees on the use of these technologies.

Keyword: Customer Relationship Management; Performance of Deposit Money Banks, South-East, Nigeria.

1.1 Introduction

The performance of the banking sector is a function of various variables. According to Karr (2022) banks worldwide are putting in measures aimed at improving their performance. Karr (2022) observes that these measures in essence revolve around better cost management practices, improved customer relationship management, improved product mix to increase the target market, informed and improved pricing decisions. This shows that the use of CRM in the banking sector is being adopted at a global perspective. Adiele and Gabriel (2018) on the other hand attribute the improved performance of the global banking sector on advancement of technology. Adiele and Gabriel (2018) argue that customer relations is a major and fundamental factor that can substantially affect the performance of a bank. This indicator measures how successfully a company achieves its goals and fulfills its mission. Organizational performance relates to the start of a scenario and the attainment of a given goal, which can encompass numerous objectives such as market share, sales volume, employee motivation, customer satisfaction, and quality level, among others (Boisvert, 2015). Because organizations play such a significant role in our everyday lives, they are a key aspect for developing countries. As a result, many economists consider organizations and institutions to be engines of economic, social, and political progress. As a result, one of the most important variables in management research is organizational performance, which is likely the most important measure of organizational performance. Despite the fact that the concept of organizational performance is commonly utilized in academic literature, defining it due to its many definitions is difficult.

In the 1950s, organizational performance was described as the extent to which organizations met their objectives when considered as a social system (Georgopoulos & Tannenbaum, 2017). At the time, performance evaluations were primarily concerned with work, people, and organizational structure. Performance was described as an organization's capacity to exploit its environment for obtaining and utilizing limited resources later in the 1960s and 1970s, when corporations began to explore new ways to measure their performance (Yuchtman-Yaar & Seashore, 2017). Several studies have identified the necessity of sustaining a strong relationship with customers. However, the Nigerian banking industry adopts customer-centric strategies in order to fully maintain and enhance this relationship with existing customers for the survival of banks (Roy and Shekhar, 2020). The evolution in telecommunications and technology services may offer many challenges to CRM. To survive in this dynamic and competitive business environment in the banking sector it is pertinent to provide an environment where customer relationships are effectively managed. Thus, customer relationship management is a critical source of gaining competitive advantage and superior performance in business organizations. Despite CRM having been found to enhance competitive performance, prior studies have highlighted the important effect and relationship between CRM and firm performance. To our knowledge, relatively few empirical studies have examined CRM on local firm performance. Most reviews are based on foreign firms and this could be due to the paucity of information on the geographical location. It is therefore worthwhile to fill the literature gap by examining customer relationship management and organizational performance of deposit money banks in South-East, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problems

The major problem that necessitated this study arose from the fact that most organizations especially banks do not fully appreciate the concept of customer relationship management and as such fail to commit both human and financial resources to its implementation. The lack of understanding could be attributed to the lack of knowledge, inexperience staff to manage customer information together with a lack of commitment on the part of employee, political

interference, as well as poor regulation of the banking industry. The lack of understanding of the concept underscores the position of most Scholars who have opined that the problems associated with customer relationship management is: lack of guidance, poor strategy, lack of employee buy-in, no accountability, insufficient resources, poorly trained employees, poor technology, weak policy, weak business environment, poor motivation of staff, policy inconsistency, poor corporate governance, poor knowledge management and sharing, poor information storage and failure to obtain executive support for the project. Hence, the key to achieving sustainable advantage lies in delivering high quality service those results to satisfaction. Most companies are aiming for good customer relationship, which means better service to the customer thereby making the customers remain loyal. The forgoing challenges affect the performance of banks. It is against this background that this study seeks to investigate effect of customer relationship management on the performance of banks in South- East, Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of customer relationship management the performance of deposit money banks in South-East, Nigeria. Specific objectives seek to:

1. Examine the effect of customer attraction on marketing performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
2. Investigate the influence of services quality management on **financial** performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
3. Assess the effect of technological innovation on **task performance** of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
4. Determine the influence of customer retention on **operational performance** of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
5. Establish the effect of customer satisfaction on **contextual** performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
6. Ascertain the effect of customer orientation on **product** performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

1.4 Research Questions:

1. To what extent does customer attraction affect marketing performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria?
2. How does services quality management influence **financial** performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria?
3. To what degree does technological innovation affect **task performance** of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria?
4. What is the influence of customer retention on operational performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria?
5. To what extent does customer satisfaction affect **contextual performance** of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria?
6. To what degree does customer orientation affect **product** performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria?

1.5 Hypotheses

- H₀¹: Customer attraction has no positive significant effect marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria?
- H₀²: Services quality management has no significant positive influence on financial performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
- H₀³: Technological innovation has no significant positive effect on task performance of

- deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
- H0⁴: Customer retention has no significant positive influence on operational performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
- H0⁵: Customer satisfaction has no significant positive effect on contextual performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria
- H0⁶: Customer orientation has no significant positive effect **product** performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

1.6. Significance of the study:

The study will be of great significance to a number of stakeholders: Organizations, deposit banks industries and other service companies, employees and management, students, academicians, institutions, entrepreneurs.

Organizations: Organizations who hitherto have been relying on customers complaints or praises as a measure of their dissatisfaction or satisfaction. Those organizations that investment in customer relationship management as a wasteful venture. This study will therefore uncover the inherent benefits that accrue from customer relationship management. It will help organizations to be committed to its implementation as a strategy towards their organization growth.

Banks Sector and Other Service Companies: The study will help the banking sector and other service companies to be able to stand competition in the midst of increasing demand and awareness by customers of their rights and privileges. This customer relationship management will help deposit money banks stand all the challenges associated with globalization in this regard.

Employees and Management: The study will help employees and management of organizations as well as potential investors to appreciate the mileage their organizations attend if they inculcate in their strategy and culture a holistic embrace of customer relationship management.

Students and Academicians: It is pertinent to also state that this study will be beneficial to students, academicians, institutions, entrepreneurs and all those who may want to know more about customer relationship management.

1.7. Scope of the study:

Content Scope: The content scope of the study will be delimited to customer relationship management and performance of deposit money bank. In addition, the unite scope covered all the customers of deposit money bank in South-East, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.0 Conceptual Review

2.1 Customer relationship management (CRM) has been an inevitable movement in the financial sector and other organizations because it represents the way customers want to be served and offers a more effective and efficient way of conducting business. Customer relationship management in the service industries is viewed on how organizations offer the best services to their customers to maintain and retain a good relationship with them. Zablah (2015) emphasized five points of view for defining Customer relationship management (Process, strategy, Philosophy, ability and technology). Zablah, Bellenger, and Johnston (2015) defined CRM as a philosophy involving customer loyalty as key to business profitability. To achieve loyalty, firms must shift their focus from getting customers to

retaining customers (Reichheld, 2016). CRM as a philosophy directs organizations to build customer centric cultures and to organize around customers (Piccoli, Connor, Capaccioli, and Alvarez, 2018; Hasan, 2018). CRM as strategy, attention is directed to maximizing the use of organizational resources towards a favorable market position. Under this perspective, Manal (2015) supported most researchers that not all relationships are good, and that customers who contributed the highest value to the firms deserved more attention from managers (Ryals, 2015). Customer relationship management as a process involves the collection of tasks or activities that help organization achieve desired business outcomes (Hammer, 2021).

Rababah, Mohd and Ibrahim, (2020) opined that customer relationship management is the working of a customer-oriented culture by which a strategy is made for gaining, upgrading and holding of customers which is powered by an information technology application. The aim is to achieve a mutual benefit for both the organization and the customer. Kotler and Armstrong (2015) defined CRM as the overall process of building and maintaining profitable customer relationships by delivering superior customer value and satisfaction. This definition seems to include the broad-based essence of marketing, wherein value and satisfaction are prominent.

Customer Attraction: is the noun to the verb attract, which basically means “to cause interest or pleasure and to pull someone towards you by the qualities you have, especially positive and admirable ones” (Cambridge Dictionaries). The basic argument is that customer attraction is and has been one of the most dominant concepts in the social psychology and social exchange literatures. Social exchange was pioneered by George Homans in the 1950s and came to life as an offspring of social psychology and sociology (Lambe, Wittmann, & Spekman 2001).

Service Quality: Kotler (2019) defines service as any act, satisfaction or experience that one party can offer to another. According to Lovelock and Wirtz (2022) services are economic activities that provide time, place, form, utility, problem solving while bringing about a change in, or for, the recipient of the service. Service possesses the characteristics of perishability, intangibility, inseparability and heterogeneity. Razak (2018) described quality services as "a measure of whether the level of service provided meets the expectations of its customers" considering that prosper of a high-quality service means adapting to the expectations of customers on a permanent basis.

Customer orientation: is the knowledge of customers and target customers to be able to create superior value consistently superior to them. Another definition is customer orientation consist of a set of beliefs that it provides customer benefits in the first place (Matsuo, 2016). Customer orientation is the willingness to help customers to assess their needs and appropriate decisions order right by them, provide services that meet customer needs, and avoid high-pressure sales tactics (Lee et al, 2021).

Technology Innovation: This refers to the computing capabilities that allow the organization to collect, organize, save, and use data about its customer. Technology is one of the key factors in implementing CRM process. Peppard (2019) suggested that technological advances were currently showing ability and growth in e-business and CRM.

Customer Satisfaction: is an important CRM variable that must not escape our empirical scrutiny. Strictly speaking, customer satisfaction is central to successful application of the marketing concept. Many company mission statements and marketing plans are designed around the goal of increasing customer satisfaction (Fournier and Mick, 2019). Customer

satisfaction can be defined as "the extent to which a product's perceived performance in delivering value matches a buyer's expectations

Customer Retention Customer retention is a measurement of how many customers remain loyal to one company over time. Retained customers are less expensive for companies to retain than new customers who have to go through research and development, marketing campaigns, promotion costs, etc., all over again for new customers. Customer retention is seen as an obligation by a customer to carry out business transactions with a particular firm on a regular basis (Hansemark & Albinsson, 2022). In addition, Molapo and Mukwada (2021) have ascertained that firms are all out to foil attempts by customers to switch retailers and indirectly retain them. In addition, Erdis (2019) has established that firms direct their marketing efforts to please their current customers in order to retain them and foster long-term relationships with them. Armstrong and Kotler, (2018).

Organizational Performance

The concept of organizational performance is based upon the idea that an organization is the voluntary association of productive assets; including human, physical, and capital resources, for the purpose of achieving a specific purpose. Those providing the assets will only commit them to the organization as long as they are satisfied with the value they receive in exchange, when compared to alternative uses of the assets. As a result, the essence of performance is the creation of value. When the value created by the use of the contributed assets is equal to or greater than the value expected by those contributing the assets, the assets will continue to be made available to the organization and the organization will continue to exist (Eckerson, 2016 and Opara & Nwulu, 2019).

Marketing Performance: Marketing performance is the metrics and outcomes that marketing departments look at to determine how well their marketing activities are doing at achieving the goals in their marketing plans. Marketing performance is the alignment between the marketing team's stated goals and objects versus actual results. It is measured using a selection of metrics and key performance indicators, including return on investment, cost per sale, and cost per lead, conversion rate, and customer lifetime value. Marketing performance, it may be seen that a system that incorporates nonfinancial measures into new financial ones is urgently required (Dublinsky & Hansen 2016).

Financial Performance: Financial performance refers to a measure of how well a firm uses assets from its primary mode of business to generate revenues, while non – financial is a long-term operational objective that emphasizes the importance of increasing customer loyalty, attracting new customers and enhancing the image and reputation of a form (Blazevic and Lievense 2015). It is also to create better profits and sales performance especially the financial service sector. Investing in Customer Relationship Management (CRM) enhances a stronger, more trusting relationship between the customer and the organization (Morgan and Hunt, 1994) as well as improved organizational performance.

Product Performance: Product performance an aspect of market performance that denotes the quality and performance of existing products and firms' records with respect to the development of new products (Sanchez & Elola, 2021). Product Performance ranks product sales based on revenue performance to inform your sales team which products are selling well. At the same time, you should rank the poorest performing products to determine which products are failing to resonate with your customers (Sanchez & Elola, 2021).

Task performance: Task performance is broadly indicated by the successful completion of assigned tasks, the number and quality of work, skills and knowledge of the performer, and

the managerial abilities of planning, organizing, problem-solving, monitoring, and decision-making. Task performance can be defined as the effectiveness with which an employee performs activities that contribute to the organization's technical core, either directly by implementing a part of its technological process, or indirectly by providing it with needed materials or services (Borman & Motowidlo, 2018).

Operational Performance: Operational Performance of the organization focuses on observable indices like customer satisfaction and loyalty, the firm social capital, and competitive edge derived from capabilities and resources. Of the organization focuses on observable indices like customer satisfaction and loyalty, the firm social capital, and competitive edge derived from capabilities and resources (Voss, Åhlström & Blackmon 2017). Operational Performance refers to the process of measuring a firm's performance against standard or prescribed indicators of effectiveness, efficiency, and environmental responsibility such as, cycle time, productivity, waste reduction, and regulatory compliance.

Contextual performance: Contextual performance encompasses all such actions which extend beyond the prescribed task roles and can manifest in social, organizational or psychological realms. This performance is associated with indicators like initiative, extra tasks performed, resourcefulness, enthusiasm, motivation, creativity, commitment and interpersonal relationships. Contextual performance is defined as the activities that employees carry out to contribute to the social and psychological core of an organization.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on Contingency Theory by Burns and Stalker (1961) and Institutional Theory by Dacin, 1997.

2.2.1 Contingency Theory

Contingency Theory by Burns and Stalker (1961), as an important management concept may have started as early as 1960s thanks to the work published by Burns and Stalker (1961), Thompson (1967), and Lawrence and Lorsch (1967), it is undeniable that, over the past 3 decades, the main contributors to this theory have been from such scholars as Scott (2015), Shenhar (2021), Ginsberg and Venkatraman (1985) and Galbraith (1973). These scholars argue that organizational performance is dependent on the goodness of fit between structural and environment variables. These contingency theorists recognize that due to the nature of the environment in which organizations operate, there cannot be one way of organizing and managing businesses (Tosi & Slocum, 1984). Moreover, one of the main focal point of this study is the identification of contingency factors that can impede on or enhance CRM implementation in an emerging market context. The Nigerian markets in particular provide the required context for testing the contingency theory. Also, by contrasting CRM practices in high income, industrialized countries against emerging markets, these practices may be found to vary in different settings, which is the fundamental premise of the contingency theory.

2.2.2 Institutional Theory by Dacin, 1997

It has been well documented in the literature that an organization's effectiveness is linked to the degree of impact its environment or social context has on its strategy (Dacin, 1997). To manage this impact better, organizations adopt business practices that may stem from various external pressures exerted on them by such market players as the national or local government, competitions, the community or even the media. This adoption of management practices influenced by institutional pressures forms the basis of the institutional theory

2.3 Theoretical Exposition

Customer Attraction and Marketing Performance.

High competition in the banking sector has transformed and made banks to place great importance on customer attraction as a key factor in determining the success of the bank. This is because a customer acquisition cost is estimated to be high, due to advertising, marketing and promotions (Alsaggaf and Althonayan, 2018; Anani, 2020; Lam et al., 2022). The customer attraction strategies that have been used include opening of new branch networks and ATM facilities countrywide, as well as the extension of mobile and internet banking services to remote areas (Amin, 2016; Estrella-Ramon et al., 2016; Suki, 2018). Research results show that relationship marketing by Lnard Berry for the first time in early 1983 had been raised regarding the services, has been able to help organizations and service companies in attracting and maintain of customers that is appeared in Fontenot definition “relationship marketing to maintain customers and develop relationships more attractive of this relationship with customers (Fontenot, Hymon, 2022).

Services Quality and Financial Performance

Service quality (SQ) is viewed as an important issue in the banking industry because of its apparent relationship to financial performance (Jamali, 2017), to costs as viewed by Crosby (2019), and to profitability (Williams, Ogege and Ideji, 2022, Rust and Zahorik, 2018). Ganguli, & Roy, (2021) defined service quality in terms of key dimensions that customers use while evaluating the service provided. Service quality management could be widely regarded as a driver of corporate marketing and financial performance.

2.4 Empirical Review

Osidele, Eniola Olayinka (2021) investigated the effect of customer relationship management on customer loyalty among customers of Cadbury Nigeria. Purposive sampling was used to select 200 participants in Lagos state. Descriptive analysis, Pearson Product moment correlation, multiple regression and simple linear regression estimation techniques were employed. Findings revealed the major reasons for continuous patronage according to most of the Cadbury customers were Cadbury’s positive handling of complaint and the product performance of the company. There was a positive and significant association between each of the CRM components (brand perception, product performance, organizational trust, complaint handling and after sale services) and customer loyalty. CRM components have significant impact on customer loyalty with complaint handling and after sale service contributing significantly to their respective regression models. The study therefore recommended that Cadbury Nigeria Limited should pay greater attention to the perceived value of its products to customers. Correspondingly, they must ensure that more priority be placed in responding to and dealing with the complaint of their customers. These without a doubt will increase the continuous patronage of their customers and hence improve their sales performance.

Ogbeide and Ogbu (2021) investigated the influence of customer relationship management on customer loyalty in the Nigerian banking industry. The study specifically shows how trust, communication, commitment, and conflict handling influence customer loyalty in the Nigerian banking industry. A survey involving 367 customers of five selected banks in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria were obtained through the use of a questionnaire. Data generated from the sampled respondents were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results revealed that trust, commitment, communication, and conflict handling dimensions of customer relationship management positively and significantly influence customer loyalty both at the group and individuals’ levels. Based on these findings, the study recommends that management of banks in Nigeria should increase the level of commitment in delivering

services to the customers by sending wishes and personalizing services to suit the needs of an individual customer; increase the level of trust with customers by delivering services to customers as promised, with sincerity and with security; improve the quality of communication with customer through on time and accurate sending of credit alerts, and services charges; and finally, improve conflicts handling with customers, which can be done by responding to customers' complaints in just, polite, timely, sincerity and satisfactory manners.

Alam, Karim and Habiba, (2021) investigated the moderating role of customer trust in customer relationship management (CRM) components and customer loyalty relationships in the context of the banking sector in Bangladesh. Data were collected through a survey using a structured questionnaire from 350 customers of commercial banks in Bangladesh. The key finding is that all CRM components (customer orientation, customer advocacy and customer knowledge) except customer engagement have positive impact on customer loyalty. Moreover, customer trust only moderates the relationship between customer knowledge and customer loyalty, whereas other CRM components and customer loyalty do not moderate by trust.

Akpoviro, Amos, Oladipo and Adewale (2020) assessed whether product quality has significant impact on the loyalty of customer in the telecommunication industry in Nigeria. He limited the study on three major telecommunication industries which include Globacom, Airtel and MTN in Lagos. Survey research design was adopted in selecting a total of 120 respondents. Analysis of variance and correlation techniques were employed. Their findings revealed that in the telecommunication company product branding has a significant impact on a product and help in ensuring customer loyalty in the business. Also, that significant relationship exists in the telecommunication industry between the product branding and the loyalty of the consumers. The study however was based on the telecommunication company and not on food and beverage companies that is fast growing in Nigeria.

Rashwan, Mansi and Hassan (2020) investigated the relationship between management and banking electronic satisfaction using electronic loyalty. CRM were measured by trust, product performance and brand perception. The study further determined the major factors influencing the loyalty of the customers in the banks. A total of 370 respondents that are using online banking were selected using convenience sampling techniques. Confirmatory factor analysis estimation techniques were employed along with structural equation modeling. They concluded that customer dynamics impacted positively on the performance of the banks in the country and that in terms of factors influencing the relationship between electronic customer relationship management and banking satisfaction is positive. Furthermore, the study found that raising contact with customers help in improving their needs, capability and attitudes towards their job. Haghkhah, Rasoolimanesh and Asgari (2020) assess the effects of service quality, trust and commitment on customer loyalty. CRM component were measured by Trust and product performance. The study used a proportionately stratified sampling method to collect data from 350 respondents in two manufacturing companies located in Asia. The Partial Least Square Structural Equation model was employed to analyse the data retrieved from respondents. The outcome from their study reveals that positive and significant relationships exist between commitment, trust, service quality, and customer loyalty in the industry. They concluded that for the organization to ensure that their customers are loyal to their product, there is need to ensure that they provide a good service quality, ensure that they practice what they claim to be and be committed to their customer's request.

Möslein-Tröppner, Stros and Řiha (2020) examine relationship between customer loyalty and customer relationship management. Cross-sectional face-to-face survey research method was used in obtaining data from randomly selected 337 fashion shoppers. Data collected were analysed using Multiple Regression technique. The study found a significant linear relationship between product quality and customer loyalty. Furthermore, that an increase in the product quality performance of the industry goods as seen by the customer will build their trust in the industry and as a result ensure commitment to the product of the company. The study however only focused on the product performance and trust but failed to look at other components of customer relationship management.

Smaliukiene, Bekesiene and Lipciute (2020) attempted a comparison of the link between customer value (measured by functional, social, emotional and symbolic value) and customer relationships in urban centers in the peripheries. A random sample survey was used to sample a total of 364 customers across Lithuania for which a well-structured questionnaire was administered to the respondent. Exhaustive CHAID (Chi-squared Automatic Interaction Detector) technique was employed in analysing the data retrieved from the respondent. Findings from their study revealed that there exists positive relationship between customer loyalty and customer relationship management in both urban and peripheral areas of Lithuania. The study failed to use different component to measure CRM. This make it difficult to determine which of the component of CRM may be beneficial to ensure customer continuous patronage.

Ata and Toker (2022) investigated the effect of customer relationship management adoption in business-to-business markets performance in 113 Turkish companies. Three aspects were evaluated on how CRM was adopted such as CRM operations, customer focused management and CRM organization. Survey research was adopted. Pearson's correlation, regression, and analysis of variance were used in testing the hypotheses. The study reported that customer focused management and CRM operations had significant effect on customer satisfaction whereas CRM organization had no significant effect. The CRM organization dimension comprised of the structure, commitment and performance of staff which had no significant effect on customer satisfaction in B2B companies. The customer satisfaction measures in the study included improved customer relations, customers' loyalty, and the rate at which customers were acquired and retained. It showed that the business architecture is challenged when the management does not support CRM implementation.

Isalm, Yang, and Mia (2022) conducted a study to show how important it is to integrate CRM across organizations' processes and functions. A survey was done on 400 customers of four Taiwan banks and the findings showed that the customer focused performance had a significant influence on the interactions of human resource, information technology and marketing service capability. Multiple regression analysis was used in testing the hypotheses. The study discovered that business architecture capabilities such as organizational commitment facilitate the implementation of CRM.

Newby, Nguyen, and Waring, (2022) investigate how CRM technology was adopted in Small and Medium Enterprises in the retail, manufacturing and service industry in South California. The study adopted Descriptive research design. Spearman correlation test was used in testing the hypotheses. The findings revealed that it was crucial for the management team and employees to fully participate in the adoption of CRM. Again, it was shown, that CRM has been implemented by employees.

Vella and Caruana (2022) carried out a study on encouraging CRM systems usage: The study focused on bank managers in a community bank in Sweden, to understand how employees used their organization's IT capability to enhance their CRM. A total of 274 questionnaires were filled in by senior and middle managers and the findings showed that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness were important in determining the intention of service providers to use CRM systems. Descriptive Survey method was adopted and multiple regression analysis was used in testing the hypotheses. These results showed that the perception created of ease of using CRM by employees should be facilitated by management by dedicating resources towards the training of employees before the implementation of CRM. The findings highlighted that the greater the ease of use, the greater the perception of functionality, and the greater the deliberate effort to utilize

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Survey research design

Survey research design was adopted in this study. One of the advantages of using survey research is that it allows the collection of a large amount of data from a sizeable population in a highly economical way. In addition, survey research gives more control for the research process (Saunders, et al., 2018). This study will use the survey strategy because it is cross-sectional in nature and cross-sectional studies usually employ the survey strategy (Estherby-Smith, Thorpe, & Lowe, 2016).

Area of Study

This study was carried out in South East Nigeria. South-East is one of the six geo-political zones in Nigeria, consisting of Abia State, Anambra State, Ebonyi State, Enugu State and Imo State. The South East State and the indigenous language of the people is predominantly Igbo. The inhabitants of the area are mainly civil servants and business men and farmers. The rural areas are however predominantly inhabited by farmers, petty traders and craftsmen. South-East shares boundaries with Delta State to the West, Middle Belt and South-South.

Sources of Data

This study makes use of primary and secondary data. The primary source of data was collected on a first-hand basis. Primary data was collected by the researcher for the specific research purpose. This study made use of copies of questionnaire to generate the primary data. Prior to the distribution of the questionnaire, secondary data were collected from relevant literature including journals, books, research papers, conference papers, government reports, and relevant electronic data, which informed the empirical study.

3.3 Population

The population of the study comprises of the Anambra State geopolitical zone in Nigeria. Owing to the large number of Bank Branches in the study area, the researcher decided to study the employees of two branches of each of the fifteen Banks in each of the selected states of the Anambra State. The population of the employees and management of the selected Bank is two thousand seven hundred and ten (2710). A breakdown of their population is presented in the table shown below:

3.3.1 Names of Deposit Money Banks in South East

	List of Deposit Money Banks	State	Number of Employees
1	<u>Access Bank Plc</u>	ANAMBRA STATE	131
2	<u>Guaranty Trust Bank Plc</u>		120
3	<u>Ecobank Nigeria Plc</u>		110
	<u>Fidelity Bank Plc</u>		120
5	<u>First Bank Nigeria Limited</u>		150
	TOTAL		631
1	<u>First City Monument Bank Plc</u>	IMO STATE	140
2	<u>Globus Bank Limited</u>		110
3	<u>Citibank Nigeria Limited</u>		114
4	<u>Heritage Banking Company Ltd.</u>		130
5	<u>Keystone Bank Limited</u>		105
	TOTAL		599
1	<u>Union Bank of Nigeria Plc</u>	ABIA STATE	150
2	<u>Polaris Bank Plc</u>		117
3	<u>Premium Trust Bank</u>		90
4	<u>Providus Bank</u>		100
5	<u>Stanbic Ibtc Bank Plc</u>		144
	TOTAL		601
1	<u>Standard Chartered Bank Nigeria Ltd.</u>	ENUGU STATE	88
2	<u>Sterling Bank Plc</u>		112
3	<u>SunTrust Bank Nigeria Limited</u>		120
4	<u>Titan Trust Bank Ltd</u>		87
5	<u>Polaris Bank Plc</u>		98
	TOTAL		417
21	<u>United Bank For Africa Plc</u>	EBONYI STATE	140
	<u>Unity Bank Plc</u>		70
	<u>Wema Bank Plc</u>		60
	<u>Zenith Bank Plc</u>		130
	<u>Parallex Bank Ltd</u>		62
	TOTAL		462
	GROUND TOTAL		2710

Source: Human Resources of Regional Office of Each Deposit Money Bank 2023

3.4 Sample Size

Cooper and Schindler (2003), state that the size of a sample should be a function of the variation in the population parameter under study and the estimated precision needed by the researcher. The target population of the deposit money banks in the South-East, is 2710. The statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall (1973) was employed to determine the sample size. The formula states thus:

$$n = (Zx)^2 eN$$

Where n = Sample size

N = Population Figure

e = Margin error and this case= 0.05

Z = Confidence level and for 0.05 it is 1.964

N.B. Target population of the banks is 2710

Substituting the population variables of this study into the formula above, the sample size can be neatly computed as follows:

$$n = (1.964)^2 0.05 \times 2710$$

$$n = 528.45$$

Therefore, n = 529

3.4.1 Sampling distribution

Accordingly, the individual states' sample allocations were proportionately estimated as follows:

$$n_i = \frac{nh_i}{N} \times n$$

Where:

n_i = The sample estimated for i state

nh_i = Population of i state

n = the entire population of interest

n = Overall sample size for the study

Hence, with the above formula meant for estimating proportionate sample, the following figures were arrived at for the three main industrial in the study: Anambra, Imo, Abia, Enugu and Ebonyi.

$$\text{Anambra State } n_i = \frac{529 \times X}{2710} \quad 631 = 123$$

$$\text{Imo State } n_i = \frac{529 \times X}{2710} \quad 599 = 116$$

$$\text{Abia State } n_i = \frac{529 \times X \ 601}{2710} = 117$$

$$\text{Enugu State } n_i = \frac{529 \times X \ 417}{2710} = 81$$

$$\text{Enugu State } n_i = \frac{529 \times X \ 462}{2710} = 90$$

3.6 Method of Data Collection

The study used structured questionnaire as the research instrument. The questionnaire was preferred tool for this study since it enabled the researcher get views from a larger number of correspondents within a short time, thus making it easier to collect relevant information. The questionnaires contained closed-ended questions. Matrix questions that utilize the Likert rating scale were used. The questionnaire had 5 point Likert scale where the respondents were requested to tick answers based on statements given. The scale had 1 indicating strong

disagreement and 5 Strongly Agree, 4 Agree, 3 Neutral, 2 Disagree, 1 Strongly Disagree to the statements.

3.7 Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument was questionnaire, which was subjected to face and content validity procedures. For face validity, the experts in the Department of Business with special assistance of the supervisors determined the appropriateness of the instruments in measuring what they purported to measure and ensured that the instruments contained the appropriate items that could actually elicit the intended responses. Experts' judgments were also used in determining the content validity. The experts looked into the extent to which the items of the instrument were representative of the contents and behaviour specified by the theoretical concept being measured.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the questionnaire was established through the test- retest method. This involved the administration of the questionnaire to 20 employees of the customers of money deposit bank who were not intended to be included in the study. Copies of the questionnaires were administered twice within an interval of two weeks, and the same results were obtained. Two sets of responses were correlated with the use of Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.92 was obtained. This was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable. The Cronbach's alpha Reliability Coefficient is 76, 82.79, 74, 92, 80 and 0.86 respectively. Base on the threshold, they are found to be reliable for the study.

3.9 Method of Data Analysis

The need to enhance easy comprehension and analysis prompted the use of the frequency distribution table to present the data gathered. Simple percentages analysis was use to analyzing the research questions while linear Regression Analysis was use in testing research hypotheses. Probability value (P-value) measures the individual significant level of the individual independent variables. A P-value that is less than 0.05 (P-value < 0.05) level of significance shows that the variable is significant but when the P-value is more than 0.05 (P-value > 0.05) level of significance, it shows that the variable is not significant.

3.11 Model Specification

The study is designed to assess the effect of customer relationship management on the Performance of Deposit Money Bank in South-East, Nigeria, as the study area. The model formulated for this study is a modification of the model adopted by Olaolu (2022). The regression model is represented as:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 + \beta_4 + \beta_5 + \beta_n + \epsilon \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad 1$$

Where:

Y =	Performance of Deposit Money Bank (PDMB)
β_1 =	Marketing Performance
β_2 =	Financial Performance
β_3 =	Task Performance
β_4 =	Operational Performance
β_5 =	Contextual Performance
β_5 =	Product Performance
α =	Constant Term
β =	Beta coefficients

The regression model is represented as:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X (SMM) + \beta_2 X (AMS) + \beta_3 X (SEO) + \beta_4 X (EMS) + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon \quad - \quad - \quad (2)$$

Where:

- X = Customer Relationship Management (CRM)
- α = Constant Term
- β = Beta coefficients
- X₁ = Knowledge Management (KM)
- X₂ = Services Quality Management (SQM)
- X₃ = Technological Innovation (TI)
- X₄ = Customer Retention (CR)
- X₅ = Customer satisfaction (CS)
- X₆ = Customer Orientation (CO)
- ϵ = Error Term a

4.1 Questionnaire Distribution Analysis

Table 4.1: Questionnaire Response Rate

A total of five hundred and eighty four copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, out of which five hundred copies of questionnaire were returned properly filled and found relevant to the study. Eighty four copies of questionnaire were not properly filled. Therefore, the analysis in this section was based on the five hundred relevant copies which represent 85.6% of the entire copies (500). The section covers A the demographic features of the respondents. The section B analyzed the data relevant to research questions.

ITEMS DISTRIBUTED	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
Copies of the questionnaire distributed	529	100
Copies of valid questionnaire Returned	500	85.6
Copies of invalid questionnaire	29	14.4
Total	529	100

Author's compilation 2023

4.2 Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

In this section, the demographic features of the respondents such as gender, marital status, age bracket, educational qualification and working experience are presented and analyzed, based on (400) valid copies of returned questionnaires were presented in the table below.

4.2 Demographic Data

In this section, the demographic features of those that participated in the study were presented and analyzed. The result is presented in table 4.2 below:

Table 4.2 Demographic Features of the Respondents

	Response Category	Number of Responses	Percentage
Gender	Male	270	46.2
	Female	330	53.8
	Total	500	100.0
Age Bracket	18 - 30 years	140	16.4
	31 - 40 years	200	34.2
	41 - 50 years	120	20.5
	51 years and above	40	6.9
	18 - 30 years	500	100.0
Marital Statues	Single	250	50.0
	Married	190	38.0
	Others	60	12.0
	Total	500	100

Educational Qualification	O'Level	160	32.0
	OND/NCE	130	26.0
	B.Sc./HND	120	24.0
	M.Sc./MBA	50	10.0
	PhD/Others	40	8.0
	Total	500	100
Number of Years with the bank	Below 5 years	200	40.0
	6 - 10 years	150	30.0
	11 - 20 years	90	18.0
	21 years and above	60	12.0
	Total	500	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023/SPSS

Table 4.2 shows the demographic profile of the employees of the sampled SMEs. A higher proportion of the respondents (53.8%) are female while 42.5% of the respondents are male. Table 4.2 revealed the age distribution of the respondents. The distribution shows that 16.4% of the respondents are between the age brackets of 18 to 30 years while 180 respondents, representing 34.2% are within the age bracket of 31 - 40 years. On the same note, 20.5% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 41 - 50 years while the remaining respondents 6.8% are within 51 years and above.

Table 4.2 also shows that 50 % of the respondents are single, 38 % are married while the remaining 12% of the respondents are either divorced or separated.

Table 4.2 further shows that 32 % of the respondents have O'level as their educational qualification. The table also shows that 26% of the respondents have either Ordinary National Diploma or National Certificate on Education as their educational qualification. 24.5 % of the respondents agreed that they have either Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) or Higher National Diploma (HND). It also shows that 10% of the respondents have M.Sc./MBA educational qualifications while 8 % of the respondents have PhD as their educational qualification.

Table 4.2 shows that 40% of the respondents have been working with the manufacturing firms between zeros to five years while 30% of the respondents have worked between 6 to 10 years. On a similar note, 18% of the respondents have worked with manufacturing firms between 11 to 20 years while the remaining 12% have worked with manufacturing firms between 21 years and above.

4.4 Test of Hypotheses

4.4.1 Hypothesis One

Ho: Customer attraction has no positive significant effect marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Ho₁: Customer attraction has a positive significant effect marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.1: Regression analysis showing the effect of customer attraction on marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)		
Marketing Performance	34.044	2.662		12.786	.000
Customer Attraction	2.752	.168	.636	16.431	.000

Linear Multiple R=0.636, Linear Multiple R²=0.404, Adjusted R²=0.403, F_{1,398}=269.971

***p<0.05**

Table 4.4.1 revealed that customer attraction has a significant positive effect on effect marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. (t =16.431, p<0.05). Services quality management has no significant positive effect on **financial** performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. (t =22.613, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected. The table indicates a significant linear multiple correlation between the predictor variable (customer attraction) and marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria (r = 0.636, p<0.05).

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Customer Attraction	2.752	.168	.636	16.431	.000

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***p<0.05**

Table 4.4.1 revealed that customer attraction has a significant positive effect on effect marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. (t =16.431, p<0.05). Services quality management has no significant positive effect on financial performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. (t =22.613, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected. The table indicates a significant linear multiple correlation between the predictor variable (customer attraction) and marketing performance on deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria (r = 0.636, p<0.05).

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Services quality management has no significant positive influence on financial performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria.

Ho₁: Services quality management has no significant positive influence on financial performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria.

Table 4.4.2: Regression analysis showing the effect of Services quality management on financial performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)		
Financial Performance	36.496	1.834		19.901	.000
Services Quality Management	2.696	.119	.750	22.613	.000

Linear Multiple R=0.750, Linear Multiple R²=0.562, Adjusted R²=0.561, F_{1,398}=511.350

*p<0.05

Table 4.4.2 revealed that services quality management has no significant positive effect on **financial** performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. (t =22.613, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected. The table indicates a significant linear multiple correlation between the predictor variable (Services quality management) and financial performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria(r = 0.750, p<0.05).

Hypothesis Three

Ho: Technological innovation has no significant positive effect on task performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Ho₁: Technological innovation has a significant positive effect on task performance of Deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.3: Regression analysis showing the effect of technological innovation on task performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)		
Task Performance	31.386	2.585		12.143	.000
Technological innovation	2.908	.162	.669	17.959	.000

Multiple R=0.669, Multiple R²=0.448, adjusted R²=0.446, F_{1,398}=322.540

*p<0.05

Table 4.4.3 showed that technological innovation has a significant positive effect on task performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. (t =17.959, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected. The table reveals that there is significant linear multiple correlation between the predictor variable (technological innovation) and task performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria (r = 0.669, p<0.05).

Hypothesis Four

Ho: Customer retention has no significant positive influence on operational performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Ho₁: Customer retention has a significant positive effect on operational performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.4: Regression analysis showing the effect of Customer retention on operational performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta(β)		
Customer Relations	38.408	1.368		28.076	.000
Operational Performance	2.601	.090	.824	29.023	.000

Linear Multiple R=0.824, Linear Multiple R²=0.679, Adjusted R²=0.678, F_{1.398}=842.360

*p<0.05

Table 4.4.4 revealed that Customer retention has significant positive effect on operational performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria (t =29.023, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected. The table shows that there is significant linear multiple correlation between the predictor variable (Customer retention) and operational performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria (r = 0.824, p<0.05).

4.4.5 Hypothesis Five

Ho: Customer satisfaction has no significant positive effect on contextual performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Ho₁: Customer satisfaction has a significant positive effect contextual performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.5: Regression analysis showing the effect of Customer satisfaction on contextual performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)		
Contextual Performance	37.928	1.713		22.144	.000
Customer Satisfaction	2.523	.108	.761	23.398	.000

Linear Multiple R=0.761, Linear Multiple R²=0.579, Adjusted R²=0.578, F_{1.398}=547.467

*p<0.05

Table 4.4.5 revealed that customer satisfaction has no significant positive effect on contextual performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria (t =23.398, p<0.05). The null hypothesis is rejected. The table shows that there is significant linear multiple correlation between the predictor variable (customer satisfaction) and contextual performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria (r = 0.761, p<0.05)

4.4.6 Hypothesis Six

H₀: Customer orientation has no significant positive effect product performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

H₀₁: Customer orientation has a significant positive effect product performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.6 Coefficients for Hypothesis Six

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
B		Std. Error		Beta	
Product Performance	(Constant)	3.092	1.254	11.454	.016
Customer Orientation	.809	.071	.770	11.454	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Sales contest

Unstandardized Coefficients (Std. Error) column: Std. Error – These are the standard errors associated with the coefficients. The standard error is used for testing whether the parameter is significantly different from 0 by dividing the parameter estimate by the standard error to obtain a t-value (see the column with t-values and p-values). Here, the standard error for constant is 1.254 and that of sales contest is 0.071. These values are used to divide the B-values (unstandardized coefficients) to get the T-values.

5.1 Conclusion

Customer relationship management is the continued process of new value identification and creation with each customer and then sharing the benefits of this value throughout the life-cycle of an organization. Based on this, the study examined Customer relationship management and performance deposit money banking industry South-East, Nigeria. The data generated from Banks were studied, analyzed and showed customer attraction has a significant positive effect on effect marketing performance on deposit banks; services quality management has no significant positive effect on financial performance of deposit banks; technological innovation has a significant positive effect on task performance of deposit banks; customer retention has significant positive effect on operational performance of deposit banks; customer satisfaction has no significant positive effect on contextual performance of deposit banks and customer orientation has a significant positive effect product performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria. Therefore, the study concluded that customer relationship management has significant effect performance of deposit banks in South- East, Nigeria.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Bank management should embark on building a stronger customer attraction since it has been established that it contributes significantly to performance of deposit banks. Bank management in order to meet or possibly exceed their planned performance can in general put customer attraction first in order to ensure greater knowledge about them to be able to satisfy their needs.
2. Bank management should develop strategies to improve service quality such as meeting customers desired service levels, improving the quality services, to meet customers' needs.
3. Organizations must not only acquire the most recent and useful technology but must also train and retrain their employees on the use of these technologies.

4. Organizations should make customer orientation a policy, since customer orientation is essential to quality management, and means of maintaining good relationship with their customers as well as putting the customer first in the decision-making process.
5. The customer relationship management should building a strong capability can only work and operates adequately when the customer is satisfied. As such the satisfaction of the customers should be the key aim of deposit money banks.
6. Banks should integrate customer feedback mechanism to promote and enhance flexibility and access to customers' feedback as this is a precursor to the positioning of the banks in line with goal of not just meeting customers expectation but also surpassing same. This will increase customer satisfaction and impact positively towards improved performance.

5.3 Contribution to Knowledge

The study contributes to knowledge by expanding and modifying the structure of a model of the relationship between customer relationship management and organizational performance enshrined by Olowokudejo (2019). Based on the analysis and the correlation between variable identified the research model can be constructed as shown below.

CRM is conceptualized through the five independent variables. The CRM variables selected for this study are Knowledge management, Services quality management, technological innovation, customer Orientation, and Customer satisfaction. These are the independent variables. The performance dependent variables are the organizational performance. Thus the independent variables have positive or negative effects on the organization performances of the banks. The positive significant influence on organization performance is a function of the conformity to the various theories of customer relationship management because one theory cannot guarantee optimal performance of the bank's operations.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Research

Future researchers should consider conducting a similar study in all the banking industry in Nigeria. This will allow the researchers to establish the most common customer relationship management practices used by the banks and how these practices relate to performance of the banking industry.

A similar research should be conducted using both primary and secondary sources of data whereby the researchers can use financial measures of performance such as sales growth, market share and return on assets. This will enable the researchers to estimate and quantify the amount of sales growth which is realized as a result of adoption of customer relationship management practices.

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